

Original Research

The Role of Customer Perceived Value, Brand Trust and Service Personalization in Shaping Customer Loyalty

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Abstract

This study investigated factors influencing customer loyalty in three-star hotels in Dodoma City, focusing on customer perceived value, brand trust, and service personalization. Qualitative data, collected through purposive sampling and thematically analyzed, revealed significant disparities in customer perceived value. A majority of the participants expressed dissatisfaction with pricing and alignment of services, signaling areas for hotel service enhancement. Transparent communication and consistent service delivery emerged as crucial for fostering brand trust, while personalized experiences positively impacted customer loyalty, highlighting the importance of tailored amenities and attentive staff. Recognizing the importance of meeting customer expectations, hotels emphasize personalized services and clear communication to enhance satisfaction and loyalty. Additionally, quantitative data collected from 96 respondents using stratified random sampling and analyzed through multiple linear regressions indicated that neither customer perceived value nor brand trust significantly correlated with customer loyalty. This suggests that variations in these factors alone do not adequately explain changes in loyalty, hinting at a more unique and context-dependent relationship. However, a notable positive correlation was observed between service personalization and customer loyalty, indicating that improvements in personalization significantly influence higher levels of loyalty. Thus, hotels should focus on tailoring services and amenities to align with individual customer preferences and needs, thereby enhancing loyalty and fostering positive recommendations. Also, hotels should prioritize transparent pricing, consistent communication, and responsive customer engagement. The study provides fresh insights into customer loyalty dynamics within Dodoma City's three-star hotel sector, offering valuable knowledge to aid hotel management in devising effective strategies to bolster customer loyalty.

Keywords: Brand trust, customer loyalty, customer perceived value, service personalization, three-star hotels.

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Introduction

The global hotel industry serves as a significant economic driver, contributing substantially to revenue generation, tourism development, job creation, and overall economic growth. This impact is felt across both developed and developing nations. The industry encompasses a diverse range of services, including accommodation, food and beverage, transportation, and entertainment, all of which collectively bolster the growth of the tourism sector (Yang, Mao, & Tang, 2018). In developed countries, the hotel sector is a vital economic catalyst, making a substantial contribution to income generation and enhancing GDP (Basrowi, Ali, & Suryanto, 2023).

In the Tanzanian context, the hotel industry has experienced escalating competition. The PwC Hotel Outlook (2018-2022) projects a growth rate of up to 8.2% in the Tanzanian hotel sector by 2022 (Calicchio, et al., 2022). Despite this optimistic forecast, a significant challenge persists: the loss of customers due to factors such as inadequate customer care services (Calicchio, et al., 2022). Dissatisfaction stemming from poor customer care services serves as a compelling catalyst driving customers to seek alternative hotel options. Thus, providing exceptional customer care services becomes a strategic imperative for hotels striving to maintain a competitive edge and cultivate customer loyalty (Calicchio, et al., 2022). Customer loyalty is crucial for establishing enduring customer relationships and sustaining the existing customer base within the competitive landscape of the hotel industry (El-Adly, 2019). Therefore, it is imperative for hotel operators to understand the complex factors influencing customer loyalty to effectively refine and focus their strategies.

Previous studies have consistently emphasized the considerable influence of hotel location and service quality on customer loyalty. Both business and leisure travellers have stressed the crucial importance of location and service quality in their choice of hotels, overall satisfaction, and subsequent loyalty (Yang, Mao, & Tang, 2018). Furthermore, service quality has been identified as a key factor driving customer satisfaction, thus impacting customer loyalty (El-Adly, 2019; Libent & Magasi, 2024). The symbiotic relationship between customer satisfaction and loyalty has been evident in the hotel industry (Kandampully and Suhartanto, 2000; Libent & Magasi, 2024). However, the complex interplay between service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty continues to evolve, offering a dynamic field for exploration (Mason and Nassivera, 2013). Another equally critical factor, perceived consumption value, demands serious consideration from hotel operators. Customers continuously evaluate the benefits derived from services against the price paid, making perceived consumption value a pivotal factor influencing customer loyalty (Ko, 2016).

Customer loyalty has emerged as a crucial determinant of success for hotels, characterized by patterns of repeat purchasing behavior, positive word of mouth, and recommendations. Such loyal customers demonstrate deeper commitment and emotional attachment to the organization (Stephen, 2020). Despite the recognized significance of customer loyalty, hotels within the Tanzanian hospitality industry, including those in Dodoma city, confront challenges in maintaining this loyalty. Some hotels, notwithstanding their provision of quality services and facilities, grapple with low

customer retention rates, which in turn result in decreased revenue and diminished market share (Calicchio, et al., 2022). For instance, Ngalesomi (2017) revealed that over 60% of visitors at New Dodoma Hotel expressed only moderate satisfaction with the level of customer loyalty. Furthermore, there exists a notable scarcity of research specifically examining the factors influencing customer loyalty in Tanzanian hotels. The existing literature (Wangchan & Worapishet, 2019; Basrowi, Ali, & Suryanto, 2023) predominantly concentrates on global or regional contexts, thereby overlooking the unique market dynamics of Tanzania. Consequently, a significant knowledge gap persists regarding the factors affecting customer loyalty in the Tanzanian hotel industry, particularly within Dodoma city.

This study aims to address the identified gap by investigating the factors that influence customer loyalty in Three-Star Hotels in Dodoma. The study aims to examine the effects of Customer Perception of Service Value, determine the influence of brand trust, and explore the influence of service personalization on customer loyalty within this context. The research questions guiding this investigation are: What is the role of customer perception of service value in shaping customer loyalty? How does brand trust affect customer loyalty? And what is the influence of service personalization on customer loyalty in three-star hotels in Dodoma City, Tanzania? Understanding these factors will enable hotel managers and marketers to make informed decisions and implement appropriate strategies, potentially leading to improved customer retention rates, increased revenue, and enhanced market share for hotels in Tanzania.

Literature Review

Theoretical review factors affecting customer loyalty

This study is guided by two complementary theories: the Expectation Disconfirmation Theory (EDP) sheds light on customer satisfaction and value perceptions, while the Trust-Commitment Theory underscores the emotional and relational dimensions of brand trust, both pivotal in shaping customer loyalty within Dodoma City's three-star hotels. Oliver (1980) introduced the Expectancy-Disconfirmation Theory (EDP) as a foundational framework for evaluating customer satisfaction. This theory suggests that customers establish purchase expectations based on the anticipated performance of goods and services, which then serve as a benchmark for evaluation. Confirmation occurs when outcomes align with these expectations, while disconfirmation arises from disparities between expectations and outcomes, leading to either satisfaction or dissatisfaction (Yi, 1990). EDP extends beyond satisfaction to elucidate customer value creation. Positive disconfirmation, where perceived value surpasses expectations, fosters enhanced satisfaction, repeat purchases, and loyalty. Conversely, negative disconfirmation, where perceived value falls short, results in dissatisfaction and reduced loyalty. Thus, effectively managing customer perceptions of value is crucial for positively influencing customer loyalty (Yi, 1990). While EDP offers valuable insights into the role of customer satisfaction and value perceptions in shaping loyalty through expectation and outcome comparisons (Oliver 1980; Yi, 1990), loyalty also includes emotional and trust-based dimensions as explained by the Trust-Commitment Theory (Wang et al., 2020; Morgan & Hunt, 1994).

The Trust-Commitment Theory, primarily focuses on the relationship between brand trust and customer loyalty. This theory posits that trust is a crucial element in fostering customer loyalty towards a brand. When customers consistently experience positive interactions with a brand, they are more likely to develop a sense of commitment, leading to increased loyalty (Wang et al., 2020). Trust is cultivated over time through the brand's reliability and perceived alignment with customers' interests. This cultivated trust promotes heightened brand loyalty, as customers become more likely to repurchase from and advocate for brands they trust (Morgan & Hunt, 1994). Moreover, the theory underscores the role of emotional commitment in nurturing customer loyalty. Emotional commitment, which surpasses rational factors like price or features, binds customers to the brand, rendering them more resistant to competitive offers or challenges (Morgan & Hunt, 1994).

Empirical review on factors shaping customer loyalty

This section explores an empirical review on factors influencing customer loyalty, examining studies across various industries and geographic regions to uncover key drivers such as perceived value, trust, satisfaction, and brand image, shedding light on their significance in shaping consumer behaviour and fostering loyalty. To begin, Heung & Ngai (2008) examined Chinese restaurants, employing structural equation modelling (SEM) to assess how perceived value and customer satisfaction mediate the relationship with customer loyalty. The results indicate that perceived value and customer satisfaction serve as mediators between value-related benefits and customer loyalty. The findings underscore the pivotal role of perceived value and customer satisfaction as mediators between value-related benefits and customer loyalty in Chinese restaurants. The study suggests further research in exploring how the aforementioned mediating factors operate in different cultural and industry contexts within the hospitality sector. Also, El-Adly (2019) conducted a study on perceived value, customer satisfaction, and loyalty in the hotel industry focusing on urban hotel guests context, utilizing SEM and purposive sampling techniques for sample selection. Surveys were administered to gather data, which underwent quantitative analysis, including regression analysis. The findings indicated significant positive relationships between perceived value, customer satisfaction, and loyalty among urban hotel guests. These findings suggest strong positive links between perceived value, customer satisfaction, and loyalty among urban hotel guests, highlighting the importance of prioritizing these factors to cultivate customer loyalty in the hotel industry.

Besides, Hasan et al. (2014) investigated the impact of perceived value and trust on customer loyalty in Sabah, Malaysia, utilizing SEM. The sample population was drawn from consumers in this Sabah, selected through stratified random sampling techniques, with data collected via surveys. Quantitative analysis methods, including path analysis, were applied for data analysis. The findings revealed a positive and significant influence of both perceived value and trust on customer loyalty in Sabah, Malaysia. The findings highlight the crucial role of perceived value and trust in driving customer loyalty in Sabah, Malaysia, emphasizing their significance in shaping consumer behaviour in the region. In a similar vein, Dayanti et al. (2019) conducted a quantitative study in Indonesia to explore the impact of brand image and brand trust on customer satisfaction and loyalty. The study utilized convenience sampling techniques to select the sample population, with data

gathered through structured questionnaires and analysed using regression technique. The findings revealed significant positive associations between brand image, brand trust, customer satisfaction, and loyalty among Indonesian consumers. These results underscore the importance of cultivating a strong brand image and fostering trust to enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty in the Indonesian market. Furthermore, Azizan & Yusr (2019) conducted a quantitative analysis in Malaysia, investigating the relationships between brand trust and brand image. The study employed convenience sampling techniques to select the sample population, and data were gathered through surveys. Utilizing correlation analysis and other quantitative methods, the study revealed significant positive correlations between brand trust and brand image, indicating that a favorable brand image is associated with higher levels of brand trust among consumers in Malaysia. These results suggest that building and maintaining a positive brand image can contribute to fostering trust in the brand, which, in turn, can influence consumer perceptions and behaviors.

Rudzewicz & Strychalska-Rudzewicz (2021) conducted research in Poland, investigating the impact of brand trust on consumer buying behavior and loyalty in the sports apparel industry. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the study combined qualitative interviews and quantitative surveys, with data collected through purposive sampling techniques. The results indicate that brand trust significantly influences purchasing decisions and fosters loyalty among consumers of sports apparel brands in Poland. The findings emphasize the importance of building and maintaining trust through consistent product quality and transparent communication. Marketers can leverage brand trust as a competitive advantage in this industry. Thus, the study offers valuable insights into consumer behaviour and highlights the need for further research to explore demographic and cultural influences on brand trust and develop strategies for enhancing it within the sports apparel market. In addition, Omoregie et al. (2019) examined the Ghanaian retail banking sector to understand factors influencing customer loyalty, employing quantitative methods and random sampling techniques for data collection. The findings indicate that satisfaction, service quality, and trust as significant drivers of loyalty. These results suggest that retail banks in Ghana should prioritize investments in personalized services, enhance service quality, and build trust to foster customer loyalty and maintain competitiveness.

Al Adwan et al. (2021) conducted a quantitative analysis in Jordan, focusing on online shopping behavior and its implications for customer loyalty. Through convenience sampling techniques, data were gathered via online surveys and analyzed by correlation analysis. The study revealed that online shopping behavior significantly impacts customer loyalty within the Jordanian context. These findings emphasize the critical need for businesses to understand and adapt to changing consumer preferences in the online realm to maintain competitiveness and enhance customer retention. Also, Arshad (2016) conducted research in Pakistan, exploring the impact of customer satisfaction on image, trust, and loyalty in the banking sector. Employing a mixed-methods approach, the study integrated qualitative interviews and quantitative surveys. Purposive sampling techniques were used to select the sample population, and data were collected through both interviews and structured questionnaires. Thematic analysis was employed to analyse the interview data qualitatively, while regression analysis and other quantitative methods were utilized for survey data analysis. The findings present an information that customer

satisfaction significantly affects image, which in turn influences trust and loyalty in the banking sector. These results underscore the importance for banks in Pakistan to prioritize customer satisfaction initiatives, as they not only shape the bank's image but also foster trust and loyalty among customers.

Based on these findings, a research gap emerges concerning the factors influencing customer loyalty within the Tanzanian hotel industry, particularly in Dodoma city. Despite the growing competition and projected growth in Tanzania's hotel sector, challenges persist regarding customer retention due to issues like inadequate customer care services. Moreover, existing literature primarily focuses on global or regional contexts, overlooking the unique market dynamics of Tanzania. Consequently, there is a scarcity of research specifically examining factors influencing customer loyalty in Tanzanian hotels, highlighting the need for studies tailored to this context. This study aims to bridge this gap by investigating the factors shaping customer loyalty in Three-Star Hotels in Dodoma, focusing on Customer Perception of Service Value, brand trust, and service personalization. Understanding these factors will enable hotel managers to implement strategies for improved customer retention rates, increased revenue, and enhanced market share in Tanzania's hotel industry.

Conceptual framework

Reviewed empirical studies indicate that most of the existing literature has been conducted in different cultural and market contexts, such as Malaysia, Ghana, and Pakistan, leaving a significant gap in understanding customer loyalty within the unique context of Tanzanian hotels. This study seeks to fill this gap by undertaking primary research among Tanzanian hotel customers, specifically in Dodoma city. The study aims to explore how customer perception of service value, brand trust, and service personalization influence customer loyalty within three-star hotels, as depicted in Figure 1 of the Conceptual Framework.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

Research Methods

Research design

This study utilized a cross-sectional research design. This approach was chosen due to time and budget constraints, enabling efficient data collection and analysis at a single point in time. A mixed-methods design was employed, combining quantitative and qualitative methodologies to examine the effect of customer perception of service value, brand trust, and service personalization on customer loyalty within three-star hotels in Dodoma City, Tanzania. The study focused on the staff and customers of selected three-star hotels in Dodoma City, the capital city of Tanzania. Dodoma was chosen as a study area because of its role as a business and administrative hub, and its attraction to visitors seeking central government and parliamentary services, as well as investors. The staff and customers of these three-star hotels in Dodoma served as the primary units of analysis due to their direct interaction and influence on service delivery.

Sampling

A sample size of 96 customers was selected from various three-star hotels in Dodoma City. The sample size was calculated using Williams and Eaton (2017) formula:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{\lambda^2}$$

In the study, n represents the sample size, p stands for the maximum potential proportion of customers (50%), $(Z\alpha/2)^2$ indicates the 95% confidence interval, and λ^2 denotes the maximum allowable error (10%).

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 0.5(1-0.5)}{0.1^2} = 96$$

$$0.1^2$$

The study employed stratified random sampling to select customers from three different hotels in Dodoma City, ensuring a representative sample from various subgroups. This method was chosen to capture a broad range of customer experiences and perspectives. Additionally, purposive sampling was used to interview 21 customers, 6 hotel managers and 5 hotel owners, allowing for targeted and insightful data collection from users and individuals with specific knowledge and expertise relevant to the study.

Data Collection

A structured questionnaire, utilizing a five-point Likert scale, was employed to gather quantitative data. This method was chosen to systematically collect standardized responses from a large sample of customers, providing quantifiable insights into these key variables. Interviews were conducted with hotel staff responsible for customer services as well as with customers to gain in-depth qualitative insights into the impact of customer perception of service value, brand trust, and service personalization on customer loyalty. This method was selected to capture the staff's firsthand experiences and perspectives, complementing the quantitative data collected through the questionnaire.

Data analysis

For the quantitative data obtained through the questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive statistics. This approach was chosen to summarize and present the main features of the data, providing a clear and concise overview of customer perceptions of service value, the role of brand trust, and service personalization within three-star hotels in Dodoma City, Tanzania. Additionally, multiple linear regressions were utilized to determine significant relationships between the independent variables (customer perception of service value, brand trust, and service personalization) and the dependent variable (customer loyalty).

The model is presented by the equation:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1CPV + \beta_2BT + \beta_3SP + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where;

In the regression model, Y predicts customer loyalty, with β_0 as the Y-intercept. β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 represent the estimated effects of customer perceived value (BCPV), brand trust (BT), and service personalization (SP) on Y, respectively. A random variable (ε) captures other factors influencing customer loyalty beyond the model's predictors.

Qualitative data from purposive sampling interviews underwent thematic analysis. First, interviews were transcribed verbatim. Then, the data was reviewed to identify themes on customer perception of service value, brand trust, and service personalization. Initial codes were generated and organized into themes, which were refined for accuracy. A comprehensive analysis was then conducted to understand factors affecting customer loyalty in selected hotels.

Reliability and validity test

Reliability testing was conducted to assess the internal consistency of the measurement scales used in the study. Data reliability was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha test, with values above 0.7 indicating good reliability.

Table 1. Reliability testing

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
CPSV	.722	16
HBT	.954	9
CP	.948	9

The Cronbach's Alpha coefficients were calculated for each variable: Customer Perceived Value (CPSV), Brand Trust (HBT), and Service personalization (CP) demonstrated good reliability with Cronbach's Alphas of 0.722, 0.954, and 0.948 respectively across their respective items, as indicated in Table 1. These coefficients suggest that the items within each variable were consistently measuring the same underlying construct, indicating a reliable measurement for subsequent analysis.

To ensure the validity of the research instruments, specifically the questionnaires, a pilot study was conducted to assess accuracy and make any necessary corrections. This approach ensured that respondents found the questionnaires user-friendly and straightforward to complete, resulting in precise and valid data for the study. Also, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin was run to confirm the data's suitability for factor analysis and findings are indicated in Table 2.

Table 2. Validity testing

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.880
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3467.329
	df	561
	Sig.	.000

The KMO measure of sampling adequacy produced a value of 0.880, indicating that the data was appropriate for factor analysis. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, with an approximate chi-square value of 3467.329 and 561 degrees of freedom, resulted in a significant p-value of 0.000. This confirms that the correlations among variables were sufficiently strong to make factor analysis meaningful.

Findings

Descriptive statistics and qualitative data

The role of customer perceived value on customer loyalty

Table 3 illustrates the perceptions of value among respondents regarding the services provided by selected three-star hotels in Dodoma City, Tanzania, and its subsequent impact on their loyalty, utilizing a five-point Likert scale from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree," with frequencies and percentages provided.

Table 3. Customer perceived value on customer loyalty

S/N	Factor & Statement	S. Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	S. Disagree
	Function Value					
1	The hotel's services satisfactorily meet my practical needs.	12	37	5	39	3
2	I consider the hotel's functional aspects beneficial and valuable.	11	31	10	38	6
3	The hotel's services match my expectations and preferences.	9	23	21	35	6
4	The hotel's amenities and services enhance my overall experience effectively.	4	22	34	27	9
	Price Value					

S/N	Factor & Statement	S. Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	S. Disagree
5	I find the hotel's services reasonably priced for their quality.	13	21	2	54	6
6	The hotel's services provide good value for the money.	4	19	7	57	9
7	I perceive the pricing of the hotel's services as reasonable and justified.	5	23	13	41	14
8	The affordability of the hotel's services adds to my satisfaction as a customer.	9	18	11	43	15
	Social Value					
9	I feel connected to the social environment at the hotel.	21	24	32	16	3
10	The hotel's atmosphere and social interactions enhance my overall experience.	17	37	39	2	1
11	I value the social opportunities the hotel offers.	17	38	28	12	1
12	The social aspects of the hotel's social aspects strengthen my loyalty as a customer.	19	34	29	10	4

In terms of Function Value, a majority of respondents expressed agreement that the hotel's services adequately meet their practical needs and requirements, with 12.5% strongly concurring and 38.5% generally agreeing. However, a notable 40.6% disagreed, highlighting a significant discrepancy between the hotel's offerings and customer expectations. Moreover, while many acknowledged the functional aspects of the hotel as beneficial and valuable, a significant proportion did not share this sentiment. Additionally, a substantial number of respondents disagreed that the hotel's services align with their expectations and preferences, pointing to an apparent misalignment between the hotel's offerings and the customers' desires. delivery. A key informant B expressed dissatisfaction with the hotel's functional value, stating,

“The amenities provided by the hotel often fall short of meeting our basic needs and expectations. Despite the hotel's claims of offering quality services, we frequently find ourselves facing issues that disrupt our stay” (Key informant B interviewed on August 12, 2023).

This sentiment aligns with the findings, indicating a significant gap between the perceived functional value of the hotel's services and the actual customer experiences.

Most respondents (56.3%) disagreed that the price they pay for hotel services matches their quality expectations in terms of value. Similarly, 59.4% disagreed with the proposition that the hotel's services provide good value for the money spent. Furthermore,

a significant number of respondents disagreed with the notion that the pricing of the hotel’s services is both reasonable and justified. This underscores the ongoing difficulty in achieving a harmonious balance between pricing and perceived value, aligning with the insights of Basrowi, Ali, & Suryanto (2023). A key informant C remarked,

“The prices of their offerings are excessively high, making them unaffordable for many customers. This often leads us to opt for lodges instead of the hotels. Even though the accommodation costs are high, the quality of the rooms fails to meet our expectations and remains merely average” (Key informant C interviewed on August 12, 2023).

This feedback highlights a significant disconnect between the perceived value and the pricing of the hotel’s services, which may contribute to the challenges faced by the hotels in retaining customers and ensuring their satisfaction.

Regarding Social Value, a significant portion of respondents feel a sense of belonging and connection to the hotel’s social environment, with 21.9% strongly agreeing and 25.0% agreeing. The majority also expressed that the hotel’s atmosphere and social interactions positively influence their overall experience. However, a significant number of respondents were undecided regarding the hotel’s atmosphere and social interactions, suggesting potential ambiguity about the social value provided by the hotel. A key informant F highlighted concerns regarding the hotel’s social value, stating,

“While the hotel promotes a social environment, it often feels superficial and lacks genuine connection. The social interactions offered by the hotel don’t always resonate with our expectations of a welcoming and engaging atmosphere” (Key informant F interviewed on August 14, 2023).

This feedback resonates with the study’s findings, revealing potential inconsistencies in the hotel’s delivery of social value and the customers’ perceptions and experiences.

The role of brand trust on customer loyalty

By analyzing respondents’ views on transparent communication, product and service quality, and brand recognition, the results from Table 4 offer valuable insights into the relationship between brand trust and customer loyalty.

Table 4. Effect of brand trust on customer loyalty

Factor	Yes		Moderate		No	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Transparent Communication						
Unclear Communication on Hotel Policies and Services Breeds Customer Doubts.	54	56.3	12	12.5	30	31.3
Lack Of Transparency in Pricing, Fees, Or Service Changes Undermines Trust.	56	58.3	5	5.2	35	36.5
Effective And Transparent Communication Channels Are Essential.	63	65.6	0	0.0	33	34.4

Factor	Yes		Moderate		No	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Product And Service Usage						
Discrepancies Between Promised and Delivered Features Erode Trust.	79	82.3	0	0.0	17	17.7
A Disparity Exists Between the Quality and Value of Products/Services.	71	74.0	11	11.5	14	14.6
Their Offerings Suffer from Poor Quality and Effectiveness.	58	60.4	28	29.2	10	10.4
Deductions						
Unfamiliarity With the Brand Name Hinders Engagement.	21	21.9	14	14.6	61	63.5
A Discrepancy Exists Between Perceived Reputation and Actual Service Quality.	51	53.1	25	26.0	20	20.8
Failing To Foster Trust and Loyalty Among Customers.	61	63.5	17	17.7	16	16.7

Concerning Transparent Communication, a majority of respondents (56.3%) expressed concerns about unclear communication regarding hotel policies and services, leading to doubts and uncertainties. A key informant H echoed this sentiment, stating,

“The hotel’s communication about policies and services is often unclear and inconsistent, leading to confusion and doubts among customers”. Also, hotels should be upfront about their amenities. It’s disappointing to arrive and find there’s no hot water for a shower. They should inform customers about these details to set the right expectations, rather than letting them find out on their own in the room” (Key informant H interviewed on August 16, 2023).

Additionally, 58.3% of respondents felt that the lack of honest and open communication about pricing, fees, or changes to services negatively impacts their trust in the brand. However, a substantial 65.6% acknowledged the presence of adequate and transparent communication channels, which could potentially foster trust and enhance loyalty among customers.

Regarding Product and Service Usage, a significant 82.3% of respondents indicated inconsistencies between the promised features of a service or product and its actual delivery. Moreover, 74.0% felt that there is a noticeable gap between the quality and value of the products or services provided. Additionally, 60.4% perceived the quality and effectiveness of the hotel’s offerings as poor, which could significantly erode trust and loyalty among customers. A key informant L commented on Product and Service Usage, saying,

“The hotel frequently fails to deliver on the promised features of their services, leading to disappointment among customers. The quality and value of the products or services often fall short of expectations, which undermines trust and satisfaction” (Key informant L interviewed on August 13, 2023).

In terms of Deductions, 63.5% of respondents indicated a lack of familiarity with the brand name, which could hinder the establishment of brand trust. Furthermore, 53.1% felt there is a misalignment between the hotel’s perceived reputation and its actual service quality, and 63.5% believe that the hotel does not effectively build customer trust and loyalty. A key informant A shared insights on Deductions, stating,

“Many customers are not familiar with the hotel’s brand name, which makes it challenging to build trust. Additionally, there seems to be a disconnect between the hotel’s perceived reputation and the actual quality of service provided. The hotel’s efforts to build customer trust and loyalty appear ineffective” (Key informant A interviewed on August 15, 2023).

These findings resonate with prior research by Basrowi, Ali, & Suryanto (2023) and Yang, Mao, and Tang, (2018), emphasizing the need for hotels to proactively address challenges to build, sustain, and strengthen customer trust. The findings highlight several critical areas where the hotels in Dodoma City need to improve to build and maintain brand trust, ultimately influencing customer loyalty. The lack of transparent communication, inconsistencies in product and service delivery, and misalignment between perceived reputation and actual service quality emerge as significant challenges. Addressing these issues is crucial for enhancing brand trust and fostering long-term loyalty among hotel customers in Dodoma City.

The role of service personalization on customer loyalty

The analysis explores how personalized experiences impact customer perceptions and loyalty decisions, revealing the link between hotels’ efforts to cater to individual preferences and their influence on customer loyalty. The data in Table 5 reveals how service personalization is implemented in these hotels.

Table 5. Influence of customer personalization on customer loyalty

Factor	Yes		No	
	freq	%	freq	%
Collect and Record Preferences				
Hotel staff gather and store customer preferences	67	69.8	29	30.2
Customers’ requests and preferences are recorded and considered.	71	74.0	25	26.0
Hotel personnel ask about customers’ preferences during their stay	63	65.6	33	34.4
Personalize Amenities				
Tailored recommendations for activities and dining.	79	82.3	17	17.7
In-room experience is personalized	70	72.9	26	27.1
Offer Options				
Flexible check-in/out and room choices.	61	63.5	35	36.5
Customers select package add-ons.	23	24.0	73	76.0
Personalized local suggestions given by staff.	37	38.5	59	61.5

The table 5 indicates the impact of customer personalization strategies on fostering customer loyalty on hotel services. Firstly, it elucidates the significance of collecting and recording customer preferences. According to the data, the majority of respondents, approximately 70%, positively acknowledged hotel staff's initiative in gathering and storing customer preferences, indicating its potential in enhancing customer loyalty. Similarly, recording and considering customers' requests and preferences during their stay received a favorable response from 74% of the participants, underlining the importance of personalized attention in cementing customer loyalty. However, while such efforts were largely appreciated, there was still a notable minority, around 30%, who did not perceive them favorably, hinting at potential areas for improvement in personalization strategies.

Also, the table sheds light on the role of personalized amenities in influencing customer loyalty. Notably, tailored recommendations for activities and dining received a high satisfaction rate of 82.3%, while the personalized in-room experience was positively reported by 72.9% of respondents. These findings underscores the importance of tailoring amenities to meet individual customer needs effectively to enhance loyalty within hotels. However, options like customers selecting package add-ons and personalized local suggestions showed lower levels of satisfaction, indicating areas that may require further refinement to better align with customer preferences.

Lastly, the table highlights the impact of offering options on customer loyalty. While some options, such as flexible check-in/out and room choices, were met with a relatively balanced response, with around 64% of respondents acknowledging them positively, other options, such as customers selecting package add-ons, received predominantly negative feedback, with only 24% expressing approval. Similarly, personalized local suggestions provided by staff received mixed reviews, with a notable 61.5% of respondents expressing dissatisfaction. These findings indicate that while offering options can be beneficial, they need to be carefully tailored to meet customer preferences and expectations to effectively contribute to customer loyalty.

A marketing manager G from the hotel survey commented,

..... *“In our marketing department, we consistently aim to provide promotions, including cost reductions, especially during special occasions like holidays....* (Key informant G interviewed on August 18, 2023)

In a similar vein, to solidify on the existing offerings, one of the managers commented,

“..... *we tailor the customer experience to meet individual preferences and needs, from gathering and noting specific customer preferences to offering personalized amenities and local suggestions. Our goal is to enhance customer satisfaction, build trust, and foster loyalty by delivering a more personalized and memorable stay.*” (Key informant K interviewed on August 18, 2023)

Findings and Discussions on Inferential Statistics

The chapter provides a comprehensive analysis of the factors influencing customer loyalty in selected three-star hotels in Dodoma City, using multiple regression analysis. The model summary in Table 6 indicates a very strong relationship between the predictors (Service personalization, Customer Perceived Value, and Brand Trust) and the dependent variable, Customer Loyalty.

Table 6. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.954 ^a	.910	.907	.359889
a. Predictors: (Constant), Service personalization, Customer perceived value, Brand trust.				
b. Dependent Variable: Customer loyalty				

The R Square value of .910 means that 91.0% of the variance in customer loyalty is accounted for by these predictors, while the Adjusted R Square, at .907, adjusts this value slightly to account for the number of predictors in the model. Overall, the model demonstrates a robust fit, with the predictors significantly explaining the variance in customer loyalty, underscoring the importance of service personalization, perceived value, and brand trust in influencing customer loyalty within the selected three-star hotels in Dodoma City.

Table 7 presents the results of an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for a regression model examining the predictors of customer loyalty. The regression model is highly significant with an F-value of 310.976 and a significance level (Sig.) of .000, indicating that the predictors, including Service personalization, Customer perceived value, and Brand trust, collectively have a significant impact on customer loyalty.

Table 7. ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	12083.318	3	4027.773	310.976	.000 ^b
	Residual	1191.588	92	.12.952		
	Total	13274.906	95			
a. Dependent Variable: Customer loyalty						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Service personalization, Customer perceived value, Brand trust.						

Table 8 presents the results of the multiple regression analysis aimed at understanding the relationship between customer loyalty and three predictor variables: Customer Perceived Value, Brand Trust, and Service personalization.

Table 8. Regression Output on Customer Loyalty

Model		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-2.802	3.044		-.920	.360
	Customer Perceived Value	.068	.059	.042	1.156	.251
	Brand trust	.108	.095	.094	1.136	.259
	Service personalization	.964	.097	.844	9.974	.000**

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Loyalty

$$Y = -2.802 + 0.068CPV + 0.108BT + 0.964SP + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

The regression output indicates that customer loyalty (Y) is influenced by customer perceived value (CPV), brand trust (BT), and service personalization (SP). Each unit increase in CPV is associated with a 0.068 increase in loyalty, while a similar increase in BT leads to a 0.108 increase. However, service personalization has the most substantial impact, with each unit increase resulting in a 0.964 rise in loyalty, indicating its critical role in shaping customer loyalty within the studied context.

Discussion

The role of customer-perceived service value on customer loyalty

Regarding Table 8, a t-value of 1.156 and a p-value of 0.251 indicates that the relationship between Customer Perceived Value and customer loyalty is insignificant. This implies that changes in Customer Perceived Value do not significantly explain variations in loyalty. Previous studies have emphasized the importance of Customer Perceived Value (CPV) in shaping customer loyalty (Ulusoy & Akyürek, 2022; Zeithaml, 1988). However, the findings of this study do not fully support these established views. This inconsistency aligns with other research that has produced mixed results on the impact of CPV on customer loyalty. For example, Smith and Bolton (1998) reported that CPV did not significantly predict customer loyalty in the telecommunications sector. This indicates that the connection between CPV and customer loyalty might be more complex and context-dependent than previously thought.

The lack of a significant relationship between CPV and customer loyalty in the context of the hotel industry in Dodoma has important implications for hotel business and strategy theory and practice. Hotel businesses in Dodoma may need to re-evaluate their customer loyalty programs. Instead of focusing solely on enhancing CPV to foster loyalty, hotels in Dodoma should consider a broader range of influential factors in this market. This might encompass elements like service quality, brand reputation, customer emotions, and customer experience, which have been identified as significant predictors of customer loyalty in prior research (El-Adly, 2019). Given that the influence of CPV on customer loyalty appears to be context-specific, it is essential for hotel businesses to tailor their

strategies to the unique characteristics and needs of their customers. This could involve conducting market research to pinpoint the most crucial factors for their clientele and developing effective strategies to address these needs. Moreover, the study's findings indicate that CPV is not the sole determinant of customer loyalty in Dodoma's hotel industry. Therefore, hotels should adopt an integrated approach to customer loyalty management, taking into account various factors that could impact customer loyalty, including service quality, customer satisfaction, and brand image (Morgan & Hunt, 1994).

The role of brand trust on customer loyalty

Regarding Table 8, the t-value of 1.136 and the p-value of 0.259 imply that the relationship between brand trust and customer loyalty is statistically insignificant. This suggests that variations in Brand Trust do not significantly explain the variations in customer loyalty in this context. Prior studies have consistently emphasized the role of brand trust in shaping customer loyalty (Mishra, 2023). Mishra's findings revealed that the empathy aspect of service quality exerts the strongest positive influence on a hotel's brand name and image, while assurance has the least significant impact. These results indicate that for hotels, especially those in the three-star category examined, enhancing service quality is crucial for strengthening their brand name and image. The findings suggest that a robust brand connection is a key predictor of both trust and loyalty to the brand. Additionally, trust positively impacts brand affection, with both brand recognition and affection influencing both attitudinal and behavioral brand loyalty.

However, the results of this study diverge from these established findings. These findings resonate with other studies that have produced mixed results concerning the impact of brand trust on customer loyalty. Research has shown that while trust and customer value significantly influence satisfaction, they do not directly affect customer loyalty (Soliha, Maskur, Widyasari, & Ariyani, 2021). It was instead revealed that satisfaction served as a mediating factor between trust, customer value, and loyalty (Soliha, Maskur, Widyasari, & Ariyani, 2021). This complexity suggests that the relationship between brand trust and customer loyalty might be more unique and context-specific than previously assumed.

The absence of a substantial correlation between brand trust and customer loyalty within Dodoma's three-star hotels holds notable ramifications for hotel operational strategies and methodologies. Establishments in Dodoma may necessitate a reassessment of their methodologies for fostering and upholding brand trust. Although brand trust retains its significance, this research suggests it might not exert the primary influence on customer loyalty within this specific market. Hence, hotels might consider prioritizing alternative factors such as service excellence, customer emotions, experience, and value proposition, as highlighted in earlier studies (Omoriegbe, Addae, Coffie, Ampong, & Ofori, 2019; Ulusoy & Akyürek, 2022), to enhance customer loyalty.

The varying connection between brand trust and customer loyalty underscores the importance for Dodoma hotels to develop tailored strategies aligned with their clientele's needs. This involves thorough market research to identify key factors influencing loyalty and implementing targeted improvement plans. Additionally, the study highlights that

brand trust alone doesn't dictate loyalty, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive approach considering factors like service quality, customer satisfaction, and brand perception to effectively enhance customer loyalty (Majaliwa & Magasi, 2024; Soliha, Maskur, Widyasari, & Ariyani, 2021).

The role of service personalization on customer loyalty

As indicated in Table 8, the significant p-value of less than 0.001 ($p < 0.001$) indicates that the relationship between Service personalization and customer loyalty is statistically significant. This indicates that increases in Service personalization are strongly associated with higher levels of customer loyalty. The relationship between service personalization and customer loyalty is a pivotal aspect of contemporary marketing and business strategy. While the significant positive relationship between service personalization and customer loyalty in this study is striking, it is important to acknowledge that some studies have found contrasting results. For instance, studies have found that service personalization may not necessarily boost customer loyalty if not implemented correctly, and that excessive personalization can be intrusive and reduce customer satisfaction (Terenggana, 2024; Tong, Wong, & Lui, 2012). In contrast, the results of this study are consistent with a growing body of research that emphasizes the critical role of service personalization in fostering customer loyalty. Lei, Wang, and Ye (2024) revealed that personalized experiences substantially elevate customer satisfaction and foster loyalty. They established a correlation between actual service personalization, perceived service personalization, and customers' behavioral intentions. Similarly, Górska-Warsewicz & Kulykovets (2020) highlighted that service personalization has a beneficial effect on customer loyalty in the context of social commerce, emphasizing the need for managers to focus on creating memorable brand experiences and fostering enduring relationships. Thus, the hotels have to enhance the overall customer experience by tailoring services and amenities that meet individual preferences and needs of each customer. This customized approach aims to create a more memorable and satisfying stay for customers, ultimately fostering greater loyalty and positive word-of-mouth recommendations.

The significant positive relationship between service personalization and customer loyalty carries several valuable implications for hotel business and strategy theory and practice. Firstly, the findings emphasize the importance of integrating service personalization strategies into hotel service offerings. Hotels in Dodoma and beyond should prioritize understanding and recognizing the unique needs and preferences of each customer. This could involve implementing tailored services, personalized marketing communications, and customized customer experiences to enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty. Secondly, the results accentuate the role of technology in facilitating service personalization efforts. Hotels can leverage technology, such as data analytics, customer relationship management systems, and artificial intelligence, to collect, analyze, and utilize customer preferences effectively. This can enable hotels to create more targeted and meaningful customer experiences, ultimately contributing to enhanced customer loyalty. Lastly, the findings highlight the need for a shift from standardized offerings to more personalized and individualized services in the hotel industry. Hotels should focus on developing and implementing personalized service strategies that resonate with their target customers, thereby fostering stronger relationships and loyalty.

Conclusion

This study investigated the factors influencing customer loyalty in three-star hotels in Dodoma City, focusing on customer perceived value, brand trust, and service personalization. Qualitative findings revealed significant disparities in customer perceived value. A majority expressed dissatisfaction with fairness in pricing and alignment of services, signaling areas for hotel service enhancement. Transparent communication and consistent service delivery emerged as crucial for fostering brand trust, while personalized experiences positively impacted customer loyalty, highlighting the importance of tailored amenities and attentive staff. Efforts to boost customer satisfaction and loyalty through personalized services and transparent communication were recognized, stressing the necessity for hotels to effectively address customer expectations and preferences. Meanwhile, quantitative findings indicate that neither customer perceived value nor brand trust significantly correlated with customer loyalty. This suggests that variations in these factors alone do not adequately explain changes in loyalty, hinting at a more unique and context-dependent relationship. This implies that hotels should prioritize aspects such as service quality, customer emotions, and experience to reinforce loyalty, rather than solely relying on customer perceived value and brand trust. However, a notable positive correlation was observed between service personalization and customer loyalty, indicating that improvements in personalization significantly influence higher levels of loyalty. Therefore, hotels should focus on tailoring services and amenities to align with individual customer preferences and needs, thereby enhancing loyalty and fostering positive recommendations. These findings underscore the importance of context-specific analysis and the need for a holistic approach when formulating strategies to enhance customer loyalty in the competitive hospitality landscape. Furthermore, the study provides fresh insights into customer loyalty dynamics within Dodoma City's three-star hotel sector, offering valuable knowledge to aid hotel management, stakeholders, and policymakers in devising effective strategies to bolster customer loyalty.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are proposed for various stakeholders in the hospitality sector. Government and policymakers should collaborate with industry stakeholders to establish guidelines for transparent communication and develop training programs to enhance service quality in three-star hotels. The hotel industry and stakeholders are advised to invest in technology for personalized customer experiences, implement CRM systems to gather and utilize customer preferences, and foster collaborations with local attractions and businesses to offer personalized local recommendations. Also, hotels can improve their communication strategies by emphasizing transparency in pricing and services, ensuring consistency across all communication channels, and actively engaging with customer feedback to demonstrate reliability and responsiveness. Customers are encouraged to engage with hotels by providing feedback and participating in loyalty programs to improve services and enjoy personalized benefits. Tourism boards and promotional agencies are recommended to collaborate with hotels to market unique local experiences and cultural aspects. Lastly, hospitality associations should organize workshops and seminars to educate hotel owners,

managers, and staff on the significance of service personalization and share best practices to inspire and empower hotels to adopt strategies that enhance customer loyalty.

Limitations and areas for further study

It is crucial to acknowledge the limitations of this study, primarily its single-country setting and potential cultural biases, which restrict the generalizability of the findings to other countries and cultural contexts. Cultural aspects can significantly influence perceptions of customer perceived value, brand trust, and service personalization. Therefore, future research should aim to replicate the study in diverse cultural settings to enhance the generalizability of the findings. Further studies could explore the impact of cultural and regional factors on customer loyalty in three-star hotels across different regions of Tanzania, analyze how cultural preferences, expectations, and social norms shape customer perceptions and loyalty behaviors, and investigate the integration of emerging technologies like artificial intelligence, chatbots, and data analytics to enhance personalized customer experiences. Additionally, future studies in the hospitality industry could explore how the relationship between perceived customer value, brand trust, service personalization, and brand loyalty is mediated by customer satisfaction.

Author Contributions

Mwanamkuu Maghembe, an MBA student, spearheaded the research, overseeing tasks such as data collection and analysis, under the guidance of Chacha Magasi, the supervisor. Despite their distinct roles, both played pivotal parts in guaranteeing the research's success.

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